

Teaching Infection Control to Students of Architecture: Defining a Needed Pedagogy and Technique

Abstract:

Context: The world has been reeling under the COVID-19 pandemic. This also led to infection control being a matter restricted to healthcare facilities and to every building which has any form of stranger interaction or public gathering. Architecture students must be taught basic infection control in their formative years.

Aims: There are two aims of this study. First, to define pedagogy for teaching Infection Control to undergraduate students in architecture. Second, to take feedback from students after the course about the program's effectiveness.

Settings and Design: An elective was proposed in the Department of Architecture in the School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi, for a semester from August 2020 to December 2020. Fourteen students in the fourth and fifth year of the Bachelor of Architecture course were offered this elective. This paper discusses nine innovative exercises the tutor conducted during the elective course. These include theory-oriented and design-based practices that ground infection control methods in the students who are being trained to be architects.

Methods and Material: The elective used a unique nine-point technique to teach infection control to undergraduate architecture students. At the end of the program, the tutor provided the students with a feedback survey based on five points Likert Scale. The feedback was evaluated using basic arithmetic.

Results: Seven of the 11 responded that the elective content was unique and was not already taught in other subjects of the Bachelor of Architecture curriculum. Six students out of 11 reported somewhat of a no when questioned regarding the awareness of infection control in the built environment.

Conclusions: The students provided positive feedback to the survey and responded positively to the suggestion of including this elective in the standard curriculum for architecture students.

Keywords: Infection Control, Architectural Education, Pedagogy, Post Pandemic Buildings, Design

Introduction:

Electives are a great way to test new pedagogical techniques and subject matters. On successful runs, these can either become compulsory courses or remain electives and be taught along with other options that can be exercised by the students based on their interests and design orientations. The COVID-19 pandemic has made architects and designers rethink the process of space defining. The built environment plays an active role in the prevention of transmission of diseases [1,2]. This newfound information, though still under development, has to be quickly disseminated to architecture students to quench their curiosity and fulfill the apparent need that the pandemic has brought up. The process of integrating this elective into the curriculum is a lengthy one, where the ideas need to be tested. Alternatively, making it

part of the design problem is another approach, but that may deprive the students of the theoretical backing that a standalone elective can only bridge. Though theoretical, this elective program has a significant component that necessitates design process implementation. In architectural programs, theory and design must be given equal footing as a good theory only leads to a successful design.

The Elective Details:

The details of the elective cover students in the final and pre-final year of the five-year undergraduate program called the Bachelor of Architecture. The students have an option to undertake a joint elective taken by teachers who specialize in a particular area of study. The students are given the choice of many elective courses, out of which each student is eligible to take one. Tutors submit the electives to an elective coordinator who screens the elective proposals. A three paged document containing the introduction, course schedule, tutor information, and a bibliography of the sources are shared with the students. The suitability of the elective course for students is analyzed on primary screening. At the pre-final level, the elective proposal is shared with students, who choose according to their preferences. This elective lasts one semester, usually 16 weeks, and has a weekly class of two hours. The tutor has the freedom to evaluate the students based on either class assignments, a final term paper, or an exam. This particular elective was conducted between August 2020 and December 2020, and the evaluation mode was based only on the class assignments. The low feasibility of having a final exam resulted in online class assignments. A subjective exam in the online mode was not particularly easy in a setup conditioned to offline in-person exams.

Methodology:

The students were provided with the result of the class assignments and an opportunity to improve in the next one and be responsible for their overall grades. Fourteen students voluntarily opted for this elective titled ‘Infection Control in the ‘Built Environment.’ About nine exercises, along with tutor presentations each week, were conducted. The tutor presentations were typical and created a robust theoretical footing regarding the built environment. The unique part of the elective was an innovative set of exercises discussed as the course progressed.

The exercises taught in the course are listed as follows:

Table 1: List of exercises from one-five with relevance and methodology conducted by the tutor in the elective from August 2020 to December 2020.

S.No.	Exercise	Rationale and Methodology
1	Talking to Grandparents about their experiences of diseases and epidemics during their youth.	Infection spread is community progress, and how it spreads and how it is tackled leaves behind imprints in the minds of people. What is happening today with the pandemic has been a revision of history, as there was an influenza outbreak a hundred years ago [3]. There were also regional epidemics that occurred in other regions. People have the experience to share, which forms the basis for the future. The exercise mainly focused on developing the base of the course on past

		<p>pandemics/epidemics faced by their elders and understanding the experiences of their close ones.</p>
2	<p>Categorizing disease according to the transmission type</p>	<p>Architecture students were asked to categorize a list of diseases according to their mode of transmission. Knowing the mode of transmission is crucial as it can help us provide architectural design and engineering interventions in the built spaces. However, direct interventions can be made in the airborne, vector-borne, and fomite spread of diseases. The interventions for blood-borne, food-borne, water-borne, and others may require other medical and allied interventions. This was done to revise the elementary knowledge about disease spread that students may have forgotten. It assisted in forming the basis of the target diseases and highlighted interventions required to be studied.</p>
3	<p>Airborne Spread of Disease: Studying infection risk using the Wells-Riley Equation [4]</p>	<p>From just a qualitative overview and analysis of the airborne spread of diseases, this exercise enabled the quantification of the probability of infection. This became the thumb rule equivalent, empirical-based approach, which would help the students make back-of-the-envelope calculations, a sort of a ready reckoner in the design of ventilation strategies and systems.</p> <p>Methodology: The students were given types of congregational spaces to be studied. They were introduced to the Wells-Riley equation. From a design problem familiar to the students, they were asked to find the area of the space under the study. They were asked to do multiple iterations with changed heights of the spaces, which would affect the overall volume of the spaces. Heights and areas are decisions that architects make in the course of design iterations. They were asked to iterate the air changes per hour in the space, which eventually affected the ‘Q’ value, which defines the room ventilation rate. They were also asked to do iterations if the assumed infected person in the spaces was wearing a mask. This would reduce the quanta value as masks are a source of control of disease spread.</p> <p>Observations: The students worked on various areas like gymnasiums, banquet halls, cafeterias, airplane compartments, restaurants, auditoriums, libraries, lifts, and other spaces having some increased interactions or gatherings. There was a substantial reduction in the probability of infection spread risk when students</p>

		<p>either increased the height of the space, increased the room ventilation rate, decreased the time spent in the room, or stimulated mask-wearing by the occupants. This exercise grounded the students on infection risks through its hands-on approach.</p>
4	<p>Reading and analyzing the research paper on the spread of disease in a university dormitory.</p>	<p>A paper on the spread of the common cold in the student dormitory was shared with the students. This study was mainly chosen because students would relate better to the situation in student dormitories/hostels which they occupy. It was expected that this would serve as a direct analogy and help the students relate to the study's occupants. This paper was from research at Tianjin University. The study bore results like sensitizing students towards infection spread due to the lack of appropriate ventilation and defined the reasons signifying its importance to designers [5]. It should be noted that these students in a professional program have limited exposure to reading and writing research literature. The exercise helped them take steps in research and acclimatize themselves with research paper writing and structuring. This will create a scientific temper while appraising them with the paper's topic.</p> <p>Methodology: The research paper was provided to students for reading and analyzing. The students summarised the paper and presented short points discussed in class. It must be pointed out that for the same paper, with limited conclusions, there were diverse interpretations that the students came forward with. All the findings were correct, but most were obvious. Some, however, opened the discussion for further research possibilities in this area.</p>
5	<p>Design Exercise-1: 10 interventions in congregational spaces.</p>	<p>The students were asked to identify the possible design interventions that can be included in a typical design. The students were asked to hand draw rough interventions as sketches. It must be noted that students were not asked to do thorough full-fledged drawings as they had to be compensated for other subjects that had an extra load of work in the same semester. This was one of the first formational exercises for this course.</p> <p>Methodology: Students submitted hand-sketched interventions that can be provided in typical buildings of public use. The student discussed these</p>

interventions based on their merits and demerits in front of the class as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The Submission of the Hand Drawn Interventions by students. Credit: Aditya Agarwal/SPA Delhi

Table 2: Exercise number six with relevance and methodology conducted by the tutor in the elective from August 2020 to December 2020.

S.No.	Exercise	Rationale and Methodology
6	Design Exercise-2: Interventions in Educational Facilities. Retrofitting in a post covid scenario with spatial planning and adding disinfection facilities.	<p>Students are very well acclimatized to the environment of educational institutes. The students can suggest retrofitting arrangements which can be made in such buildings. This method focused on the hands-on approach where the integration of the learnings from the elective were utilised in the design studio. The students were provided with a typical site plan cum ground floor plan of an educational building. They were also asked to read the recent standard operating procedures released by the State Government, Central Government, and health and disaster management organizations.</p> <p>Methodology: All the students proceeded to mark interventions on the same plan. This consisted mainly of all the measures required to retrofit the space for compliance of social distancing, circulation for reduced interaction of people, and the placement of</p>

Table 3: List of exercises from seven to nine with relevance and methodology conducted by the tutor in the elective from August 2020 to December 2020.

S.No.	Exercise	Rationale and Methodology
7	Reinterpreting a webinar on Post-Covid planning of healthcare facilities.	<p>At the beginning of the course, the tutor conducted an international webinar with speakers from infection-spread research, including medical doctors, fluid dynamic engineers, space planners, and other experts. This exposed the students to a compulsory session of experts talking about the post-pandemic design of spaces, especially healthcare facilities, which are the most prone to disease spread.</p> <p>Methodology: Students were made delegates to attend the online international webinar and were given attendance points. The students were also asked to submit insights from the webinar as an assignment.</p>
8	Categorization of Biosafety with examples of BioSafety (BS) labs.	<p>The students must be taught the specialized infection-controlled spaces beside the interventions required in everyday buildings. This is already classified in terms of Biosafety levels. The students would learn about high biosafety standards in the built environment, like in BS3 and BS4 labs, which signifies Biosafety Level 3 and Biosafety Level 4, respectively.</p> <p>Methodology: Students were asked to compare the differences between the three Biosafety levels 2, 3, and 4. They were tasked to make a comparative chart of all the architectural and engineering service requirements for the three kinds of labs.</p>
9	Study of current innovation in architectural space & design, and allied products	<p>The students must be taught to unleash their imagination and look beyond what is possible. They were asked to perform a search on Google, Pinterest, social media, and elsewhere about some catchy, innovative interventions implemented in the built environment, product design, and city design in general. This would rekindle the imagination of students who should not be only bound by the current knowledge and methods but should be encouraged to look beyond.</p> <p>Methodology: Students were asked to look into social media, image repositories, Google searches, and other sources of catchy information that have shown some innovative methods in the built environment and allied areas where some intervention for infection reduction has been done. Students were asked to compulsorily</p>

		upload ten innovations in the form of one slide per innovation in a presentation. They were asked to share the presentations on their common class stream on Google Classroom. This enabled everyone to get their eyes on innovations, and a large repository was created and discussed in class.
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In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the pedagogy in the elective offered, a set of feedback questions were framed and made available to the 14 students. The feedback form was created on Google Forms which was made optional, and the students were also given the option to provide anonymous feedback. Out of the 14 students, 11 chose to give feedback, and one out of the 11 submitted anonymous feedback. The feedback form consisted of a questionnaire with six questions listed in table 4, answerable within a range of answers on five points Likert Scale.

Table 4: List of questions asked in the feedback survey created in Google Forms

S.No	Questions asked in the feedback form
1	Do you think an elective like this should be compulsory for architecture students?
2	Is the content of the elective unique, or is it already taught in other subjects?
3	Was there any new information provided on disease prevention in the built environment?
4	Was the content of the elective delivered in an easy-to-understand/grasp method?
5	Do you think there is a general awareness among architects/students on infection control in the built environment?
6	How likely will you use the principles learned in the elective in your real-life projects/academic projects?

Results:

Eleven out of 14 students answered their feedback forms. Four of the 11 strongly felt that this elective should be made compulsory for the students of Architecture, and six felt the same somewhat strongly. The remaining one stated a maybe. Seven of the 11 responded that the elective content was unique and not already taught in other subjects of the Bachelor of Architecture curriculum. 10 out of 11 students responded very strongly that new information was provided on disease prevention in the built environment. Seven strongly felt, and four somewhat strongly felt that the content delivered was easy to understand/grasp. When asked about the general awareness among architects/students on infection control in the built environment, six out of 11 felt that it was somewhat of a no. Seven out of the 11 students and four out of the 11 reported that they would somewhat strongly and very strongly use the principles learned in the elective in their real-life projects/academic projects. The students were asked to share their experience of the elective. Some general comments of the students were as follows:

‘To be honest, I haven't really considered healthy environments through architecture, and this course triggered and initiated my approach to this area.’

‘Very comprehensive and wholesome elective.’

‘I know whatever I have learned here will help me in my future career.’

‘Definitely, Wells Riley equation which assisted in quantifying the risk factor regarding various diseases.’

‘And for this elective, it is one of the subjects I enjoyed most in my five years.’

‘I feel that retaining information was not hampered here because of online teaching, unlike other subjects. That area was handled very well.’

Discussion:

It is very encouraging to see positive responses from the students who took the elective. The responses were unbiased as we saw reactions that were also critical of the process. One student suggested that an end term on a research topic would have been better than a sum of individual assignments. This elective was possible as the School of Planning and Architecture promotes the culture of allowing new and innovative ideas. Later, the school conducted seminars on a related topic and received a good response. In general, ventilation, for example, as an infection control measure, is taken less seriously, and the pandemic has brought forth its importance [6]. Other steps leading to social distancing can now be integrated into the design practice and, eventually, the curriculum.

Conclusion:

The elective on Infection Control in the Built Environment as a unique and innovative idea was a successful attempt to bring forth the new requirement into the design of dealing with the pandemic, viz the ventilation and space planning. The students provided a positive response to the elective where the majority admitted the lack of general awareness of Infection Control in the built environment. This study highlights the necessity of introducing Infection Control to architecture students in their curriculum. This shall be taken forward by other schools of design in India and elsewhere as a disciplined requirement for the students of architecture and allied building disciplines.

The subject requires an interdisciplinary approach and the integration of infection control principles needs wider dissemination, with student training being the best opportunity to do so.

Declarations:

The authors have no conflict of interest. No funding was taken for this study.

Ethics Committee Approval:

Exemption from Ethics Review: As per the National Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical and Health Research involving Human Participants released by the Indian Council of Medical Research, this study falls under the category of 'Exemption from Review' because this study comes under the category of 'comparison of instructional techniques, curricula, or classroom management methods'. Additionally, the Head of the Department, who is the second author of the paper has provided his permission for the use of classroom data.

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